

**Engaging Crowds:
citizen research
and heritage data at scale.**

**A response to the
Advisory Board Report
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by

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My understanding of the Engaging Crowds project

From the documents I have read it appears to me that the aim of the Engaging Crowds project is the production of a report on the current state of citizen research projects in UK heritage institutions, three Zooniverse projects, an indexing tool aiming to give volunteers agency to choose their pathway in those Zooniverse projects and a research project analysing data on how and why volunteers choose their pathways.

The overarching theme of this initiative seems to me to be to increase the amount of engagement as well as the diversity of people undertaking engagement with heritage institution crowdsourcing initiatives.

The following advice and feedback I am about to give is informed by my experiences as a citizen researcher and digital volunteer with various crowdsourcing projects. These experiences have shaped my beliefs, particularly the belief that to engage deeply with cultural heritage is to reuse that cultural heritage, and that any barriers hindering potential reuse of content or data held on behalf of the public by heritage institutions is to dampen the possibility and likelihood of engagement.

In this document I intend to give my response to the Advisory Board report and raise the questions I have about the report's content. I will then outline my initial response to the specific discussion points raised in the later part of the report.

Response to Report

WP3 Indexing Tool Prototype development - pg 5

I very much approve of enabling a volunteer to focus on the parts of the project they are interested in. Hopefully this tool will go some way to ensure that volunteers can focus in on an area they are interested in without losing the all important serendipitous moments that make crowdsource volunteering so interesting.

I have visions of using this tool to ensure I transcribe all the labels of specimens collected by one particular collector and therefore being able to follow them on their collecting journey via the specimens they collected. Or alternatively transcribing diary entries which deal with a particular recurring date, for example transcribing entries on how a person celebrated Christmas each year. I will be extremely interested to follow the progress of the development and implementation of this tool as I hold out high hopes that it will encourage more active engagement with citizen research projects.

WP4 Platform development - page 7

This section discusses a platform for sharing the data created by the three Zooniverse citizen research projects.

Given the reuse licensing on the various websites of the participating organisations I am wondering what the reuse licensing will be for each of the volunteer generated datasets. Will these be open access or will the reuse licenses currently used by each of the organizations on their websites apply? That is, the open government license for the National Archives, the Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commerical Use license for the Royal Botanic Garden, Edinburgh and the Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial Share Alike license for the Royal Museums Greenwich.

I ask as I am looking at all three of these Zooniverse projects from the point of view of a volunteer looking to donate my time. I am attempting to ensure I choose each of these projects instead of the numerous similar projects in Zooniverse.

One method I use to narrow the selection of projects to whom I might donate my time, is to consider the reuse license placed by the institution on my volunteer work product. If the institution allows only restrictive reuse it is unlikely I will volunteer for them. Currently, from the information I've been able to glean from the participating institutions websites, terms of use and copyright statements, there is likely only one project of the three I might consider volunteering for - the National Archives project.

Even with that organisation I admit to having concerns. In light of this I feel I should outline my specific concerns about each project.

I do this to attempt to ensure the success of each of these projects, as I believe all have worthy aims and ambitions. I am aiming to ensure that each of these citizen research projects is as successful as possible and can attract as many volunteers as possible.

WP5 Citizen Research Projects - page 8

Royal Museums Greenwich - Dreadnought Seaman's hospital records

This project is the one I am most concerned about as they mention in the report that the content they intend for volunteers to work on has been digitised and made available by a commercial website that paywalls access to the project content, that is Ancestry.com. My worry is that the transcriptions made by Zooniverse volunteers will only be made accessible through this commercial website, requiring volunteers to pay to get access to their work.

The report states that the Royal Museums Greenwich will “make the entirety of the record available digitally”. Can you explain further what that means?

Firstly, what is meant by “the record”? Is it the transcription of the document or does it also include the digital scan of the original document? Where will this record be available? How easily will volunteers be able to access and reuse the transcriptions and the resulting data they have created?

I am worried that volunteers will spend time and effort transcribing these documents only to find that they have to pay Ancestry.com for access to their transcriptions. I believe this would be unethical and it is one of my major concerns when reading about this project in the report.

In light of this I would recommend that Royal Museums Greenwich consider carefully how they draft up their “about” section explaining this project to volunteers in the Zooniverse platform. In particular I recommend a statement be made that specifically addresses the ability of volunteers to reuse data and transcriptions created by volunteers. Of course I believe this work product should be openly licensed for reuse but if this is not going to be the case, volunteers should be informed of this prior to undertaking any work on the project.

I recognise that the Royal Museums Greenwich may have entered into an agreement with Ancestry.com regarding the reuse of the digital surrogates of the original documents made by that company. If it is these scans that are being used by volunteers to create the transcriptions I recommend a statement explaining this be made in the “about” section of the project.

I have come across a similar situation to this with the Smithsonian Transcription Center’s Freedmen’s Bureau records project. Those documents were also scanned by a genealogy website but National Museum of African American History and Culture make the documents and transcriptions available at the following website: <https://nmaahc.si.edu/explore/initiatives/freedmens-bureau-records>.

I am also concerned that the way the report is written seems to indicate the focus of Royal Museums Greenwich is on creating transcription and indexing projects that benefit the Royal Museums Greenwich more than they encourage a deep engagement by volunteers with the collections of the museum. I recognise the two aren’t mutually exclusive, but the report gives the impression the Museum is more concerned about what the volunteers can do for the Museum rather than what the Museum can do to deepen the volunteer engagement with and enjoyment of the Museum’s collection.

The National Archives - Scarlets and Blues

Scarlets and Blues project summary is interesting as it focuses on explaining why this project might be of interest to a more diverse audience than it first appears. Initially I read the project description, rolled my eyes and thought “one more project about data on boys”. I’m afraid this is a hangover I suffer from, as a result of all the crowdsourcing projects I saw during the 100 year commemorations of WWI.

If institutions are keen to engage with a more diverse audience, I recommend their projects do a good job of explaining why a more diverse audience should engage. The magic words for me here in this project explanation were “exploring the changing role of women as the war progressed”.

This project seems very similar in scope to the currently active ‘Measuring the Anzacs’ on Zooniverse. See <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/zooniverse/measuring-the-anzacs/about/research>. So in a very real way this project will be competing for volunteers in Zooniverse with ‘Measuring the Anzacs’. Currently if I, as a volunteer, had a choice between the two I admit I would be more likely to pick the Measuring the Anzacs project. This is purely as a result of knowing and trusting the contributing institutions. I am confident they will ensure that project content and data is reusable by me either because the content is in the Public Domain in New Zealand or is licensed for reuse under an open creative commons copyright license.

Having explored the National Archives digital collections I admit to having the same concern with the reuse of volunteer generated data as I have with the Royal Museums Greenwich project. There appear to be many collections of content and data in the National Archives that can only be accessed by paying a subscription to a commercial website. See <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/help-with-your-research/research-guides/?letter=&search=&research-category=online>

In order to attract volunteers to this project I recommend having a statement in the 'about' section explaining their ability to reuse the data and transcriptions they are providing. Any restrictions placed on the ability of volunteers to engage with and reuse content should be made clear.

I also note that the National Archives has raised the possibility of whether the manual transcriptions made by the volunteers could be used to train a better handwritten text recognition model. If this is a likely use of the content provided by volunteers, I believe this should also be explained to the volunteers in the "about" section in the project description on Zooniverse. Volunteers should be made aware of what their volunteer contributions will be used for.

Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh - African Violets

Of the three projects the RBGE transcription project will be entering the most competitive "market" to obtain volunteers. There are numerous herbarium transcription projects both in Zooniverse as well as competing crowdsourcing sites such as DigiVol <https://digivol.ala.org.au/>.

The concern I have with this project is that RBGE licenses the reuse of their specimen data under a Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial use license. See for example <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/bf2a4bf0-5f31-11de-b67e-b8a03c50a862> As much as I admire and enjoy this institution and their work (and have participated in at least one previous crowdsourcing project of theirs), this license has stopped me from reusing and engaging more deeply with their content. As an example, because of this restrictive license, I am unable to reuse the images of their specimens in Wikipedia to illustrate Wikipedia articles on particular species of plants.

The fact that any data that I or other volunteers like me provide is going to be licensed for reuse under a CC BY NC 3.0 license would and has stopped me from volunteering for them. Instead I can easily find a similar project in Zooniverse that openly licenses my volunteer work product for all to reuse.

An example would be the New York Botanic Garden Zooniverse project

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-nybg/about/results>

The New York Botanic Garden Zooniverse project gives an “about” section that states “All contributions to this project are archived permanently in the C.V. Starr Virtual Herbarium, and made available to the world through our open-access online database: www.nybg.org/vh.”

This online database states they publish data in GBIF with images of the specimens licensed for reuse under a CC BY 4.0 license and the data under a CC0 license. See for example

<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d415c253-4d61-4459-9d25-4015b9084fb0>

I recommend that the RBGE inform potential volunteers in the “about” section of their project on the terms of reuse that would be placed on data generated by the volunteers. There may be volunteers who are unconcerned by the restrictions placed on the reuse of data created and are still prepared to volunteer.

As regards the Indexing tool I believe the potential for the successful use of it in this project is high. I can already envision situations where the volunteer might wish to transcribe all specimens of a particular species or all specimens collected by a particular collector. Also I am a firm believer in the use of dropdown lists in citizen research projects such as this as they increase not just the accuracy but also the speed of transcriptions.

Recommendations for all three Zooniverse projects

In light of the above I advise that all three zooniverse projects have an “about” statement on their project that includes information on what is the institution aiming to do with the data generated by the volunteers, what the volunteers can do with the data and content they create and also a statement on what, if anything, volunteers can do with the collection content in the project.

Ideally each project should have a specific statement telling crowdsourcing volunteers where the data they create will end up, giving a clickable link to it, and explain what reuse license will be placed on that data.

It is worth remembering that Zooniverse volunteers might not be resident in the UK so any exceptions to UK copyright law such as fair use will not apply to folk reusing content outside the UK. If volunteers are reusing the project content in their country it is their country's copyright law or if used an appropriate international copyright license that will apply. I would therefore recommend that any reuse license used be an International Creative Commons license and that it be as open as possible to encourage engagement with heritage institution's collections.

Good examples of "about" sections can be found in

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/bldigital/living-with-machines/about/research> and <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/zooniverse/measuring-the-anzacs/about/research>

Report Discussion Points

1. Do these parameters seem appropriate? Is there anything missing?

Limiting the scope of the report to the types of citizen research projects run by formal cultural heritage organisations of any size and any collection type rather than volunteer organisations may be a challenging definition to implement. I know in New Zealand we have very small but formal cultural heritage institutions that are completely volunteer run but still engage in digital citizen research. For example a volunteer run town museum who asks volunteers to photograph local sites of historic interest or conducts a bioblitz of their local area adding their observations to the iNaturalist website. The team may wish to consider whether such citizen research projects would fall within the scope of the project.

I approve of the wide net being cast in the literature review, with the review including published works, informal publications such as blog posts as well as unpublished internal reports. I am of the opinion that this will help ensure the report will elicit findings on who participates, why they participate and how heritage organisations can enhance the experience of the citizens engaging with citizen research projects.

The report may want information on not just the engagement of volunteers with the specific citizen research projects but also whether any volunteers went one step further and reused or undertook activities inspired by their participation in those research projects. That is, to consider the motivation of those volunteers who deeply engaged with content they came across as a result of their participation in the citizen research project. If the report wishes to consider this, perhaps interviews of specific participants from a variety of projects who made that extra step could be considered.

2. What is your view of how different tasks affect volunteer engagement?

Initially when first attempting a crowdsourcing project, I find the easier the task the more quickly I get up to speed. The more complex a task is initially, the less likely volunteers are to persist with that task. But the other side of this coin is that once a task becomes less challenging it can also become more repetitive and boring. In my experience, if there is a way to “level up”, that tends to make a project more engaging. For example progressing from simple tagging, to transcribing, and then on to reviewing can be a way to ensure continued engagement with a project.

3.

4. Have you had experience of 'measuring' volunteer engagement? What metrics have you had experience of using? Have they been effective? Is a survey the best way to gather this information, or should we attempt to include volunteer interviews, for example?

I have had experience in being 'measured' for volunteer engagement. That is, people who are interested in motivations and how to elicit more active volunteer engagement with their collections have had me fill out both surveys and have interviewed me. As a result I would recommend that both methods be used by the Engaging Crowds project. Interviews have obtained more nuanced information from me on both my motivations and the activities I undertake with content I have discovered through participation in citizen research projects. I would highly recommend undertaking both a survey and volunteer interviews. I also suggest interviews with those running the citizen research projects. Project organisers are likely to be able to point to those volunteers participating in their projects that are highly engaged and have taken the extra step of reusing or more deeply engaging with content and data.

5. How do we acknowledge the effect that automation has on volunteer engagement and take that into consideration when creating projects or encouraging use of crowdsourced results to train automated processes?

From my experience I have gone on a journey of being one of those volunteers who prefers to transcribe a document "from scratch", to then performing an editorial role, to then reusing the end results of the project, such as the data contained in the digital transcription, independent of the original heritage institution and its citizen research project. I believe it is a matter of designing the citizen research project in such a way that challenges the volunteer to progress and upskill.

Automation may ensure that the "from scratch" transcription work will no longer be needed. But other tasks can be designed to ensure volunteers continue to be both engaged with and contribute to the project. It may not just be editing the automated transcription, it might be a task of writing a finding aid for the content, or linking people mentioned in the content to their identifiers in genealogy sites, or interlinking content from the project to that already held in the heritage institution database.

There will always be crowdsourcing tasks that will both engage volunteers and assist heritage institutions to enrich their content and data.

I believe a citizen research project shows itself to be successful if it encourages volunteer engagement by giving volunteers the agency and confidence to reuse heritage institution content outside of the confines of the research project itself.

Of course this assumes that the heritage institution allows for the reuse of both the content the volunteer has been exposed to in the project and the enriched data volunteers have contributed. Currently I have concerns that many United Kingdom heritage institutions fall at this 'reuse' hurdle as they either partially or totally restrict reuse. In my eyes engagement is reuse and it is very difficult to have one without the other.

Automation may ensure this deepening of engagement of volunteers by assisting volunteers to undertake those activities that result in more active engagement with content.

6. In what way could we make our final report the most useful to the community?
What form could it take?

I believe the report will be most useful if it gives, not just a summary of the current state of play of citizen research projects in the UK, but also best practice recommendations on how to design a citizen research project that will be both ethical to volunteers and effective for the Heritage institution. My advice would be for the report to give recommendations on how an institution might design a project that is attractive to volunteers, that motivates volunteers to both contribute to the project and engage with project content, that delivers the results the institutions are seeking and at the same time encourages volunteers to more deeply explore and reuse both the project results and the heritage institution's content.

The report could give recommendations on the types of licensing and reuse requirements that institutions might use to better encourage volunteers to engage with both the data generated by the project, the project content and the institutions wider collections.

Perhaps a practical outcome might be a training course or training manual summarising the report and teaching interested cultural heritage institutions how to create a successful citizen research project and encourage engagement with cultural heritage institution content by implementing the recommendations of the report.

Conclusion

I hope the above response is of use and anticipate the Advisory Board meeting in October will enable further clarification and dialogue about the advisory report and the discussion points raised by the Engaging Crowds team.